

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Prasetyanti**FIRST NAME:** Anastasia**PROGRAM CODE:** MBAIO**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

DIGESTING IN A MONTESSORI WAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I let Montessori system inspired me since I work for a school that uses Montessori as their system. With the early childhood learning, a hands-on learning plays the important role of the education, it's all practical. This where I understand that when you first learn something, it will get better when you practice. A beautiful system. Referring to the Montessori system, my understanding towards the EUCLID information has become cleared when I started practice it on this response paper. As also a poetry enthusiast, I focus on how poetic a writing is. One of my favorite poetry techniques is *Onomatopoeia* which is a word imitating a sound and can be used in variety of ways giving the reader a 'hands on' feel (Hess, 2019). I imply this technique when I read through the information, let it persuade me to later on be a well-shaped minded person and have this as default setting on my writing's technique. The ACA-401 provides all information that we need to start an academic writing.

2) BE OBSERVANT

I will break down my response of EUCLID ACA-401 course:

a) Structuring

The title of "Organising Your Ideas" on the first chapter caught my mind. We often have ideas but find it hard to put them together into writing. This chapter also showed us how to write structurally. Start with the strong suggestion that we have start to work early,

define the question and analyze the task, and construct an initial plan. Then follow by researching the topic, organizing your ideas, writing, referencing, and editing the essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-4).

I love writing down my opinion on my note towards some issues and always did some research beforehand but reading the EUCLID information is making me realize that my (note) writings are just the skeleton of an actual professional paper.

b) Noticing Mistakes

I could not help but notice the mistake on the page 20 of the Period 1 course pack. The topic was about the conjunction (and). On the example one written “My favorite types of sandwiches are peanut butter and jelly, cream cheese, roast beef, and turkey club. (Formal way)” meanwhile the example two was also “My favorite types of sandwiches are peanut butter and jelly, cream cheese, roast beef, and turkey club (Modern way).” Both examples were the same, but it says “Therefore, both examples can be considered acceptable. Many teachers and grammar guides instruct that the inclusion of the second comma is optional” (EUCLID 2019, 20).

Canadian Writer’s Reference explained when three or more items are presented in a series, those items should be separated from one another with commas. Items in a series may be single words, phrases, or clauses. Although some writers view the last comma in a series is optional, most experts advise using the comma because its omission can result in ambiguity or misreading (Hacker and Sommers 2019, 260-261).

c) Great Britain vs American English

The honorifics example on the grammar, syntax, punctuation, general usage showed the difference between the U.S. and G.B. style on how to use dot after the title of Mr. or Mrs. or Dr. The Oxford Living Dictionary shows that G.B. does not put dot after the title as shown on the example that EUCLID used (EUCLID 2019, 29).

A single close parenthesis without an opening was also appeared on the sample of Difference in Usage with SBK “Pluralised Adjectives” (Ibid.).

Concept similarity example on the G.B. “bank holiday” vs U.S. “public holiday” or just “holiday”; “Boxing Day” also showed an inaccuracy. The Boxing Day term is used on the day after Christmas (26 December) and is not necessary means just a normal public holiday (EUCLID 2019, 31).

The example of insults given for the G.B. English which were “tossers” and “wankers” and had the U.S. “dorks” and “losers” as comparison showed imbalance. The words “tossers” and “wankers” are more insulting than the “dorks” and “losers” (Ibid).

d) Yiddish and Ethnic Jewish Influence

This part has given me a new knowledge, words I never heard before such as “schlep, goy, schlemiel, schlock, nebbish, shtik” (EUCLID 2019, 33).

Fairly speaking, the examples given on the EUCLID information such as ethnolect, jargons, regional variation, identity, stereotyping are purely information for the reader. This means readers would never put these phrases into their academic or professional writings (EUCLID 2019, 32).

e) The Sample Corrections to Papers

The response of the example paper that said “THINGS ARE ALWAYS SERIOUS” reminded me how different we should write in academic writing, that has to include a reference, citation, and also choosing proper words (EUCLID 2019, 36).

Critique of consistency was also found on this chapter of how we stick either to U.S. or G.B. style. We have to be mindful when we write (EUCLID 2019, 41).

3) CONCLUSION

I enjoy writing, especially when it comes to writing my opinion towards something such as the newest issue and I would always like to put it together based on facts. The EUCLID ACA-401 course teaches me how to think, structure, and research-based my writing which let me go deeper with everything.

EUCLID information has awakened my academic writing up after a long-time hiatus. What makes this challenging is, on my day to day professional life, I write formal letters to the government in Bahasa Indonesia and have the conversation with members of the school in English. Two different languages with two different structures, one of the reasons why I keep practicing my English writing way before I started this course.

Reading like a writer helps you identify the techniques writers use so that you can use them, too. To read like a writer is to pay attention to *how* a text is written and *how* it creates an effect on you (Hacker and Sommers 2019, 61). As I mentioned before as I digest information in a Montessori way which means to observe and get a hands-on experience myself. To observe then to write down your opinion does not necessary mean that you have to judge the author’s ideas, it is to understand the author’s ideas (Hacker and Sommers 2019, 63).

This period of ACA-401 course is a start-off of my critical thinking to get sharpened and also to train my self-discipline. The *non-deadlined* paper is highly convenient and giving me enough freedom but as Montessori said, “a limited freedom.” A very refreshing start for my mind. I look forward for more writing, to have in the future, a well-rounded skill of academic and professional writing.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2019. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1 (accessed March 20, 2020).

Hacker, Diana, and Nancy Sommers. 2019. *A Canadian Writer's Reference – Seventh Edition*. Boston: Bedford/St. Martin's publications.

Hess, Garry. 2019. *Poem of Quotes*. www.poemofquotes.com (accessed March 21, 2020).

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